

Synthesis of Imidazoles. Part I. Preparation of some 4(or 5)-Substituted Imidazoles

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As the condensation of ethyl 3-phthalimidoacetoacetate with alkyl (or aryl) halides fails to yield ethyl 1-alkyl (or aryl)-3-phthalimidoacetoacetates, the desired products have been prepared in satisfactory yields by condensing ethoxymagnesium salt of substituted diethyl malonate and phthalimidoacetyl chloride. The substituted acetoacetates have been hydrolysed (dil.HCl) and the corresponding aminoketones treated with potassium sulphocyanide to yield 2-mercapto-4(or 5)-alkyl (or aryl)-imidazoles. The latter have been oxidised to the corresponding imidazoles.

Imidazoles and mercaptoimidazoles (Gabriel, *Ber.*, 1893, 26, 2197) are well known for their biological activities; with this end in view some of these compounds have been prepared by us employing a more convenient method for the preparation of α -aminoketones.

The desired α -aminoketones have been prepared by ketonic hydrolysis of ethyl 1-alkyl(or aryl)-3-phthalimidoacetoacetate(IV). For the preparation of the latter, the sodium salt of ethyl 3-phthalimidoacetoacetate (this *Journal*, 1961, 38, 785) was condensed with suitable alkyl halides. This, however resulted in the formation of a deep red-coloured semisolid from which the desired compounds could not be crystallised. Hence an alternative procedure, similar to that employed for the preparation of ethyl 3-phthalimidoacetoacetate (*loc. cit.*), was employed. Ethoxymagnesium salts of substituted diethyl malonates (I) were condensed with phthalimidoacetyl chloride (II) in dry ether to afford ethyl 1-substituted-3-phthalimidoacetoacetate (IV) in satisfactory yields.

[R=Me, Et, -CH₂C₆H₅, -CH₂OC₂H₅]

Ethyl 1-alkyl (or aryl)-3-phthalimidoacetoacetates (IV) were then hydrolysed by 30% HCl. The hydrochlorides of α -aminoketones (V) on heating with an aqueous solution of KCNS afforded the mercaptoimidazoles (VI), which were purified through the mercury salts. These were then oxidised by HNO₃ (dil.), FeCl₃, etc., when the corresponding imidazoles (VII) were regenerated.

Ethyl 1-methyl-3-phthalimidoacetoacetate is soluble in hot ethanol, glacial acetic acid, ether, and benzene and gives a red colour with ferric chloride. *Semicarbazone*, m.p. 57°. (Found: N, 16.2. $C_{16}H_{18}O_5N_2$ requires N, 16.19%).

Ethyl 1-ethyl-3-phthalimidoacetoacetate was prepared by a method similar to that described above, using Mg (2.4 g.), ethyl diethylmalonate (19 g.) and phthalimidoacetyl chloride (22.4 g.). It was twice recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 70°, yield 54%. (Found: C, 62.79; H, 5.78; N, 4.62. $C_{16}H_{17}O_5N$ requires C, 63.3; H, 5.6; N, 4.41%).

The solubility of the ester and its colour reaction with ferric chloride are the same as of the preceding ester. *Semicarbazone*, m.p. 65°. (Found: N, 15.83. $C_{17}H_{20}O_5N_4$ requires N, 15.56%). *Pyrazolone*, m.p. 63°. (Found: N, 12.49. $C_{20}H_{17}O_3N_3$ requires N, 12.1%).

Ethyl 1-benzyl-3-phthalimidoacetoacetate was prepared as usual, using Mg (2.4 g.), diethyl benzylmalonate (25 g.), and phthalimidoacetyl chloride (22.4 g.). It was thrice crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 98°, yield 38.6%. (Found: C, 68.77; H, 5.01; N, 3.56. $C_{21}H_{19}O_5N$ requires C, 69.04; H, 5.2; N, 3.83%). The solubility of the ester and its colour with $FeCl_3$ are same as with the preceding esters. *Semicarbazone*, m.p. 104°. (Found: N, 13.21. $C_{22}H_{22}O_5N_4$ requires N, 13.27%). *Pyralazone*, m.p. 103°. (Found: N, 10.61. $C_{23}H_{19}O_3N_3$ requires N, 10.27%).

Ethyl 1-ethoxymethyl-3-phthalimidoacetoacetate was prepared in 57% yield by following the procedure adopted as above with diethyl ethoxymethylmalonate (22.4 g.) using the same molar proportion of the other constituents. After twice crystallisation from ethanol it melted at 108°. (Found: C, 61.74; H, 5.43; N, 4.04. $C_{17}H_{19}O_6N$ requires C, 61.26; H, 5.70; N, 4.20%).

The ester is freely soluble in ethanol, glacial acetic acid, ether, and benzene. It develops a red colour with ferric chloride. *Semicarbazone*, m.p. 112°. (Found: N, 14.52. $C_{18}H_{22}O_6N_4$ requires N, 14.36%). *Pyralazone*, m.p. 115°. (Found: N, 11.41. $C_{21}H_{19}O_4N_3$ requires N, 11.14%).

4(or 5)-Methylimidazole.—Ethyl 3-phthalimidoacetoacetate (27.5 g.) was heated with 30% HCl (200 c.c.) for 3 hours till the ester had dissolved. On cooling most of the phthalic acid separated. This was filtered, the filtrate concentrated to half the volume on a water bath, and then chilled in ice. Precipitated phthalic acid was again filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. Highly hygroscopic *hydrochloride of the aminoketone*, m.p. 75° (H_2PtCl_6 , m.p. 189°), thus obtained, was dissolved in ethanol and precipitated with ether. The precipitate was quickly filtered and dissolved in water (10 c.c.). KCNS (8 g.), dissolved in water (8 c.c.), was then added and the mixture heated on a water bath for 2 hours. It was slowly evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in warm water (100 c.c.) and treated with a saturated solution of mercuric acetate till the precipitation was complete. The light yellow precipitate of mercury complex of 2-mercapto-4(or 5)-methylimidazole was suspended in water (50 c.c.), made acidic with HCl (dil.), and H_2S gas passed. Mercury sulphide was filtered and washed twice with 20 c.c. portions of water. The combined filtrate and washings were treated with charcoal and filtered. The clear filtrate was evaporated to dryness when hydrochloride of 2-mercapto-4(or 5)-methylimidazole was obtained as a yellowish white, hygroscopic substance. This was dissolved in dry ethanol and neutralised with EtOH—KOH. Precipita-

ted KCl was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to crystallisation, m.p. 246° (lit. m.p. 245-46°), yield 3.42 g. (Found: N, 24.22; S, 28.30. Calc. for $C_4H_6N_2S$: N, 24.5; S, 28.02%). This gives 2-acetoxymercapto-4(or 5)-methylimidazole, m.p. 200° (Found: N, 15.98; S, 18.67. Calc. for $C_6H_8O_2N_2S$: N, 16.28; S, 18.60%).

2-Mercapto-4(or 5)-methylimidazole was oxidised by warming slowly with 30% HNO_3 . The light red solution slowly changed to yellow. The solution was evaporated to dryness at minimal pressure and the residue was taken in dry ethanol. This was then neutralised with EtOH-KOH and filtered. From the filtrate the solvent was removed under diminished pressure. The residue after crystallisation from ethanol-ether gave 4(or 5)-methylimidazole, m.p. 56° (lit. m.p. 56°). (Found: C, 58.69; H, 7.42; N, 34.36. Calc. for $C_4H_6N_2$: C, 58.54; H, 7.32; N, 34.15%). Hydrochloride, m.p. 119°; picrate, m.p. 164°.

4(or 5)-Ethylimidazole.—Ethyl 1-methyl-3-phthalimidoacetoacetate (14.45 g.) was hydrolysed by 30% HCl when hydrochloride of aminomethylketone, m.p. 151° (H_2PtCl_6 , m.p. 171°), was obtained; by following the procedure described above, but using 6g. of KCNS, 1.6 g. of a cream coloured 2-mercapto-4(or 5)-ethylimidazole, which started melting at 210° and decomposed at 260°, was obtained. (Found: N, 21.66; S, 25.29. $C_5H_8N_2S$ requires N, 21.87; S, 25.0%).

2-Mercapto-4(or 5)-ethylimidazole was oxidised by boiling with an aqueous solution of ferric chloride (14 g.) for 12 hours. After leaving overnight, the solution was made alkaline to litmus with 50% K_2CO_3 and filtered. The filtrate was extracted 10-12 times with 50 c.c. portions of $CHCl_3$. The combined extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was again removed. The residue was recrystallised several times with ethanol-ether when 4(or 5)-ethylimidazole, m.p. 76.5°, was obtained in quantitative yield. (Found: C, 62.19; H, 8.38; N, 29.53. $C_5H_8N_2$ requires C, 62.5; H, 8.33; N, 29.17%). Nitrate, m.p. 82°; picrate, m.p. 116°.

4(or 5)-Propylⁿimidazole.—Ethyl 1-ethyl-3-phthalimidoacetate (15.2 g.) was hydrolysed similarly and by using 6 g. of KCNS to 2-mercapto-4(or 5)-propylⁿimidazole; m.p. 184°, yield 1.3 g. (Found: N, 19.63; S, 22.36. $C_6H_{10}N_2S$ requires N, 19.72; S, 22.54%).

2-Mercapto-4(or 5)-propylⁿimidazole was oxidised by ferric chloride (14 g.) when 4(or 5)-propylⁿimidazole, m.p. 66.7°, was obtained in quantitative yield. (Found: C, 65.42; H, 9.48; N, 25.36. $C_6H_{10}N_2$ requires C, 65.46; H, 9.09; N, 25.45%). Hydrochloride, m.p. 120°; picrate, m.p. 179°.

4(or 5)-(β -Phenylethyl)-imidazole.—Ethyl 1-benzyl-3-phthalimidoacetoacetate (18.5 g.) was hydrolysed and treated with KCNS, as described above, when 1.1 g. of 2-mercapto-4(or 5)-(β -phenylethylimidazole, m.p. 260° (decomp.), was obtained. (Found: N, 13.62; S, 16.02. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2S$ requires N, 13.73; S, 15.69%).

2-Mercapto-4(or 5)-(β -phenylethyl)-imidazole was oxidised by ferric chloride (14 g.) when 4(or 5)-(β -phenylethyl)-imidazole, m.p. 81°, was obtained in quantitative yield. (Found: C, 76.70; H, 7.21; N, 16.52. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2$ requires C, 76.74; H, 6.98; N, 16.28%). Hydrochloride, m.p. 146°; picrate, m.p. 236° (decomp.).

4(or 5)-(β -Hydroxyethyl)-imidazole.—Ethyl 1-ethoxymethyl-3-phthalimidoacetoacetate (16.65 g.) was hydrolysed by HCl (dil.), as described above, and the corresponding

aminoketone was treated with KCNS (6 g.), when 1.3 g. of 2-mercapto-4(or 5)-(β -hydroxyethyl)-imidazole, m.p. 193° (lit. m.p. 193°), was obtained. (Found: N, 19.15; S, 22.63. Calc. for $C_5H_8ON_2S$: N, 19.44; S, 22.22%).

2-Mercapto-4(or 5)-(β -hydroxyethyl)-imidazole was oxidised by ferric chloride (14 g.) when 4(or 5)-(β -hydroxyethyl)-imidazole, m.p. 92° (lit. m.p. 92°), was obtained in quantitative yield. (Found: C, 53.75; H, 6.89; N, 25.43. Calc. for $C_5H_8ON_2$: C, 53.57; H, 7.14; N, 25.0%). The hydrochloride is highly hygroscopic.

Authors' sincere thanks are due to Dr. A. N. Dey for his keen interest in the present work.

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Received April 11, 1961.

